

Electronic Databases on Islam in Arabic by Al-Turāth, Jordan

Al-Turāth (<http://www.turath.com/>) is one of the most prolific publishers in the field of digital textual databases of Arabic and Islamic sources. So far they have developed and published dozens of different databases, several of which will be reviewed in what follows. At our disposal we have had access to the following titles (mostly older versions):

Group 1:

1. *Maktabat al-Akhlāq wa-l-Zuhd wa-l-Raqā'iq* (“Library of Ethics, Asceticism and Spiritual Subtleties”). 1 CD.

Group 2:

2. *Maktabat al-Adab al-'Arabī* (“Library of Arabic Literature”), Version 1 (published in 1419/1999; 1 CD); 32 books.
3. *Maktabat al-Ta'rikh wa-l-Ḥaḍāra al-Islāmiyya* (“Library of Islamic History and Civilization”). Version 1.5 (Published 1419/1999, 1 CD). 125 books.
4. *Maktabat al-'aqā'id wa-l-milal* (“Library of Doctrines and Religious Groups”). Version 1.5 (Published 1419/1999, 1 CD). 163 books.
5. *Maktabat al-ma'ājim wa-l-gharīb wa-l-muṣṭalaḥ* (“The Library of Dictionaries of Foreign, Rare and Technical Vocabulary”). Version 1 (Published 1419/1999, 1 CD). 23 books.
6. *Maktabat al-Turāth al-Siyāsī* (“Library of the Political Heritage”). Version 2 (Published in 1421/2000, 1 CD). 39 books.
7. *Maktabat 'Ulūm al-Ḥadīth* (“Library of The Sciences of Ḥadīth”). Version 1 (Published 1421/2001, 1 CD). 47 books.
8. *Maktabat 'ulamā' al-Islām* (“Library of the Scholars of Islām”). Version 1 (Published in 1421/2001, 1 CD). 62 books.
9. *Maktabat al-Ṣarf wa-l-Naḥw* (“Library of Morphology and Grammar”). Version 1 (CD 1).
10. *Mawsū'at al-Khuṭab al-Minbariyya*. (“Encyclopaedia of Friday Sermons”). (1 CD).

Group 3:

11. *al-Maktaba al-alfiyya li-l-sunna al-nabawiyya* (“Library on the Prophetical Sunna, Containing over a Thousand Books”). Version 1.5 (1 CD). Containing about 1,300 volumes, this is one of the most helpful databases for researchers on Ḥadīth.
12. *Maktabat al-fiqh wa-uṣūlih* (“Library of Jurisprudence and Its Foundations”). Version 1.5 (1 CD). Contains 900 volumes (mostly Sunnī Law).

Group 4:

13. *al-Maktaba al-alfiyya li-l-sunna al-nabawiyya* (“Library on the Prophetical Sunna, Containing over a Thousand Books”). Version 3 on 3 CDs.

14. *Barāmij al-Qur’ān al-Karīm wa-‘ulūmih*. (“Programs on the Noble Qur’ān and the Qur’ānic Sciences”). Version 3 on 1 CD.
15. *Maktabat al-fiqh wa-uṣūlih (fiqh)*. (“Library of Jurisprudence and Its Foundations”). Version 3 on 3 CDs.
16. *Maktabat al-ta’rīkh wa-l-ḥaḍāra*. (“Library of Islamic History and Civilization”). Version 3 on 2 CDs.

Group 5:

17. *al-Jāmi‘ al-Kabīr. al-Nuskha al-Dhahabiyya al-Muṭawwara* (Version 2: Advanced Golden Edition on HDD). At \$400, this is the most expensive and extensive database. Coming on an external HDD, and containing around 20,000 volumes, it apparently combines all of al-Turāth’s separate libraries.

The databases listed above have been divided into five groups because they share similar user’s interfaces. They also have similar bugs and glitches, which we will discuss in the following section.

System requirements and program installation

Early versions of the al-Turāth libraries were designed to work on the Arabic version of Windows 95 and Windows 98 (we tested them on both systems); they can also be installed on Windows XP and Vista (tested on XP Professional and Vista Professional). However, to have them installed on either of these versions of Windows, it is necessary to change some localization settings, as otherwise the Arabic will be unreadable.

Windows XP. To change settings in XP: Go to “Start” → “Control Panel” → “Regional and Language Options” → then choose Tab “Advanced” and, in section “Language for non-Unicode programs”, choose Arabic (any country). If Arabic is not available, go back to Tab “Languages” and in section “Supplemental language support” check “Install files for complex scripts and right-to-left languages”. Then choose Arabic as described above. You will need to reboot the computer.

Windows Vista. To change settings in Vista: Go to “Start” → “Control Panel” → “Regional and Language Options” → then choose Tab “Administrative” and, in section “Language for non-Unicode programs”, click “Change system locale...” and choose Arabic (any country). You will need to reboot the computer.

NB: When you change language for non-Unicode programs, some symbols in some other non-Unicode programs (German, French, Russian, etc.) will appear unreadable. To use those programs you will need to change “Language for non-Unicode programs” back to the original language.

Unfortunately, full install does not seem to work on Vista, so, you will have to be content with small install, i.e., without copying the entire database onto your hard drive. This means that

you will have to keep the CD in your CD/DVD-Rom drive, and the databases may work a little more slowly and more noisily. This, however, can be overcome by making an image of the CD that you own and running it in the virtual CD/DVD-Rom drive (e.g., by using “Daemon Tools,” a free utility). Second, if you install several different databases by al-Turāth, it may happen that some of them will stop working (a program will not start and an error message will be displayed). In this case, you will need to reinstall the database you are going to work with. This may also require some extra steps, depending on the kind of error. For more details see <http://www.turath.com/ar/> (Click at the link in the end of the line (in red script) *Idhā wājhatka/ki mashākil fī ayy min barāmijinā...*). Third, programs do not display correctly in the windowed mode and have some glitches in full-screen mode.

We have had access to four titles from the new versions of the al-Turāth databases (Version 3, Group 4). Our greatest disappointment has been our inability to run any of these programs. The problem is that these new versions require an activation number, which the user is supposed to get on the al-Turāth website (Section *Raqm al-tashghīl*), using serial numbers printed on the CDs. Unfortunately, the activation website did not recognize any of our serial numbers.

Older versions of databases often do not have an *autostart* option, so you will need to start installation manually (double click *setup.exe*, which in most cases is found in the “Setup” folder).

The texts in the databases are reproduced quite accurately¹ (typos are rare) and the pagination of the originals is preserved. Names of chapters are given in a different color, but otherwise the formatting of the original paper editions is lost. For this reason it is very tricky to discern verses of poetry in the text, and so on. Moreover, all the books lack the introductions, notes and commentaries which appear in the paper editions.

The language of interface in all al-Turāth databases is Arabic only.

¹ I was able to discover only one significant flaw in the *Maktabat al-ta'rikh wa-l-ḥadāra l-islāmiyya* (Version 1.5): some volumes of Ibn al-ʿImād's *Shadharāt al-dhahab* have been shuffled. However, it is not too difficult to get used to this. The problem must have been fixed in later versions of the database.

User's interface and basic capabilities

As mentioned above, the user's interface differs slightly among the five different groups, but the basic capabilities are the same for all databases. In every database the user can:

1. open any book from the list of books and navigate within it, either using buttons to browse pages (“*Awwal/First*”, “*Lāḥiq/Next*”, “*Sābiq/Previous*”, “*Ākhir/Last*”), or selecting a precise volume and page in order to get to a precise place, or choosing a certain chapter from a table of contents;
2. open two books in comparison mode (*muqāranāt*) and navigate within them (options are similar);
3. conduct searches of different complexity (for more on this, see the *Search* section);
4. send selected pages or search results to printer or save to text file (for more on this, see the *Search* section);
5. add comments and corrections to any page of any book;
6. customize the appearance of the text, changing fonts (adjusting size and color) and colors.

In what follows we will review all these capabilities in detail and with screenshots, taking the reader through each function step by step.

User's Interface of *Group 2* databases: Working with Database

Main Window

When the program is started, it opens the initial window (Pic. 1), where the user can see a *Main menu* and several buttons for the most often-used commands.

Main menu

1. *Milaff / File*
 - a. *Taṣaḥḥuf kitāb / Browse a book*: opens the list of books in the library (see Pic. 2 Reading Mode) and the last open book.
 - b. *Naskh / Copy* (active only in Reading Mode): opens the Copy window.
 - c. *Khurūj / Exit*: click to close the program.

2. *Baḥth* / Search
 - a. *‘Āmm* / General [search]: opens the General Search window.
 - b. *Mawḍū’ī* / Table-of-contents search: opens Table-of-contents search.
3. *Khuṭūṭ* / Fonts (active only when any book is open)
 - a. *Ḥajm al-khaṭṭ* / Font Properties: changes **font face** and size.
4. *Alwān* / Colors
 - a. *Lawn al-khalfiyya* / Background color: changes color of the background (“paper”); the default is pale yellow, as in many Arabic editions (*kutub ṣafrā*).
 - b. *Lawn al-khaṭṭ* / Font color: changes font color.
5. *Iṣḍārātunā* / Our products: open to read information on other programs developed and published by al-Turāth.
6. *Akḥṭā’* / Typos: open to make any corrections of typographical errors discovered on the currently open page.

7. *Khidmāt* / Services
 - a. *Ta’līqāt* / Comments: open to add a comment to a currently open page of the book.

- Muqāranāt* / Comparison Mode: open to compare, page by page, two different books or search results.
- Musā'ada* / Help: open to use Help, where all menu option, buttons and functions are explained (in Arabic).
- Ḥawla l-barnamaj* / About ... : open to see details about the open program (See descriptions of each program below).

Quick buttons (see Pic 1. Main Window) are simply the most commonly-used commands from the main menu, collected on a separate toolbar for prompt access ([8] *Taṣaḥḥuf* / Browse; [9] *Baḥṭh 'āmm*/General search; [10] *Mawāḍi'*/Chapter search; [11] *Muqāranāt*/Comparison mode; [12] *Musā'ada*/Help; [13] *Ḥawla*/About...).

Reading Mode

To begin working with a database, the user will usually click either *Taṣaḥḥuf*/Browse or *Baḥṭh*/Search. Clicking *Taṣaḥḥuf*/Browse will take the user to reading mode (Pic. 2).

The *Main Menu* is the same as described above.

Quick buttons are the same as described above, except for two new buttons. *Naskh/Copy* opens a *Saving/Exporting Texts* window (see below); *Ta'liq/Comment* opens a small pop-up window, where any comment can be typed in.

List of Books (Qā'imat al-kutub): Black, bold and underlined are names of sections; black normal — book titles; red normal — currently open book (double-click on any book to open it).

Table of contents of the open book (as you can see, this section does not display correctly): *al-'Unwān* (Name of the Chapter); *al-Juz'* (volume in which the chapter is located); *al-Ṣafḥa* (page on which the chapter is located).

TOC Search (search in the table of contents): type in some text, then click the *Baḥth* button (next to the search line) in order to search the table of contents of the currently open book. If any of the searched-for words are found, the name of the chapter will be highlighted. Click the *Baḥth* button again to move on to the next search result.

Text: a window where the actual text of the book is displayed. Titles of chapters are often highlighted with a different color (i.e., dark red).

List of books navigation pane: here the user can search the entire list of books for a needed book and check the bibliographical details of any title included in a certain library.

- (1) *Biṭāqa/Bibliographical details*: opens a card with all available details about the paper edition on which the currently open digital book is based (see *Pic. 3 Bibliographical details*).
- (2) *Search line (search in the list of books)*: type in some text, then click the *Baḥth* button next to the search line to search the list of books. If any of the searched-for words are found, the title of the book will be highlighted. Click the *Baḥth* button again to move on to the next search result.
- (3) *Baḥth (Search button)*: starts the search.

Reading Navigation Pane: these are buttons for navigation within the opened book.

- (4) *Awwal (First)*: click to move to the first page of [the first volume of] the book.
- (5) *Lāḥiq (Next)*: click to move to the next page of the book.
- (6) *Sābiq (Previous)*: click to move to the previous page of the book.
- (7) *Ākhir (Last)*: click to move to the last page of [the last volume of] the book.
- (8) *Juz' (Volume)*: displays the number of the open volume.

- (9) *Şafha* (Page): displays the number of the open page.
- (10) *Intiqāl* (Move to...). Fields (8) and (9) can also be used to move to a certain place within an opened book: enter the desired volume and page numbers and then click *Intiqāl* (Move to...) button in order to move there.
- (11) *Khurūj* (Exit): click to leave Reading Mode and return to the Main Window.

Bibliographical details. As mentioned above, you can review all available details about the paper edition on which the currently open digital book is based. The *Standardized Bibliographical Card* has the following fields (as a rule, not all of them are filled): (1) Title of the book; (2) Name of the author; (3) Year of author's birth; (4) Year of author's demise; (5) Number of volumes; (6) Publishing house; (7) Place of publication; (8) Year of publication; (9) Edition number; (10) Editor's name. The *Standardized Bibliographical Card* window also has a navigation pane with

which the user can move to the (11) first, (12) next, (13) previous or (14) last title. The *Ṭibā'a* Buttons (15 and 16) export bibliographical details into a text file (see *Pic. 4*): (15) exports details of the open book only, (16) exports details for all books in the library. Click (17) *Khurūj/Exit* to return to Reading Mode.

Comparison Mode (*Muqāranāt*).

Click the *Muqāranāt* button to open Comparison Mode (*Pic.5*).

In this mode you can compare, page by page, two books or search results (select the appropriate bookmark: *Qā'imat al-kutub* or *Natā'ij al-baḥth*). Click on either *Window 1* or *Window 2* to make it active, and then select a desired book or search result. The *Navigation pane* is the same as in Reading Mode and works with the active window; the *Table of Contents* button (*Intiqāl ilā mawḍū'*) opens the contents of the active book.

Conducting Searches

The search function is the most important part of every textual database. The search engines of al-Turāth databases provide many useful options and tools, which allow the user to conduct very complex searches, and to work efficiently with the search results. There are two major kinds of search: (1) General Search, and (2) Tables-of-Contents Search. These can be started by clicking the *al-Baḥth* and *al-Mawāḍiʿ* buttons respectively.

General Search

Clicking *Baḥth* (Search) opens the [General] Search window (Pic. 6).

To conduct any search, first of all, it is necessary to define the range of the search, i.e. to select the books which are to be subjected to search. Clicking (1) *Jamī* /All will move all the books in a database into the *Search Range* window (*Niṭāq baḥth al-barnāmaj*).

You have the option of limiting your search to specific books. In order to modify the *Search Range*, click (1) *Jamī* /All (it should look different now and should be called *Ilghā' al-jamī* /Delete All) again to clear the search range. Then choose a desired section in *Sections of Database*, check desired titles in the *List of Books* (*Qā'imat al-kutub*), and then click (2) *Naql* /Move to add the selected books to the *Search Range* window. Repeat this operation to select more books from other sections.

After the search range has been defined, type your query in the *Search Line* (*al-Rajā'* *kitābat al-naṣṣ* /Please enter the text). Make sure to define *Search Conditions*. The available options are as follows:

- (6). *Kalima faqat/One word only*. If this option is selected (default), no more than one word can be entered.
- (7). *Naşş/Text*. Select this if you want to search for a specific line of text. E.g., if you type *Abū Nu‘aym al-Işbahānī*, the *line* — i.e. in the same order and with no other words between them — of these three words will be found and displayed in the search results.
- (8). *Juz’ min kalima/Part of a word*: This detects all words of which your query is a part. E.g., such words as *[al-]şūfi*, *[al-]mutaşawwif*, *[al-]şūf*, *[al-]taşawwuf* etc. will be found if you type in *şwf*.
- (9). *Mufradāt mutabā‘ida [wa]/Separate words [with the Boolean operator] ‘and’*. If this search option is selected, the program will search for *pages* which contain all the words contained in your query. E.g., if you type *Abū Nu‘aym al-Işbahānī*, all pages that contain these three words — no matter in what order and no matter how many words come between them — will be found and displayed in search results.
- (10). *Mufradāt mutabā‘ida [aw]/Separate words [with the Boolean operator] ‘or’*. If this search option is selected, the program will search for *pages* which contain either word from your query. E.g., if you enter several different words into the search line, all pages which contain any of three words — no matter in what order and no matter how many words come between them — will be found and displayed in search results.

Click (3) *Tanfīdh/Perform [search]* to start search. This will open the search results window (see below). It is also possible to work with the results of a previous search: Click (4) *Ākhir natīja (Previous results)* to open previous search results; or (5) *Milaffāt baḥth (Saved search results)* to open previously saved search results. Click (11) *Khurūj/Exit* to close the Search window.

Hints on searching

Making efficient searches and taking full advantage of the database’s search capabilities require practice. Here are some hints. (6) *Kalima faqat* is convenient when you need to find something very particular and when you are sure that this word does not have any alternative spellings. Otherwise, (10) *Mufradāt mutabā‘ida [aw]* can be a helpful option. For instance, say you are searching for a particular *nisba*. Since sometimes final *yā’* is used without dots as if it

were *alif maqṣūra*, and the *hamza* over or below the letter *alif* is sometimes omitted, it may be helpful to try different spellings, such as *الاصبهاني* and *الاصبهاني* (as well as other combinations with or without *hamza* and *yāʾ/alif maqṣūra*).

(7) *Naṣṣ* is convenient for finding an exact line of text, as for example, when you need the source of a quotation. However, if you are looking for variants of a particular text, it is helpful to use (9) *Mufradāt mutabāʿida [wa]*. In this case it is useful to reduce a phrase to keywords, excluding, for example, prepositions and other words which are too generic or which may assume different forms (such as *abū*, which may become *abā* and *abī*). So for instance, if you are looking for a biographical account of *Abū Nuʿaym al-Iṣbahānī*, the option of (7) *Naṣṣ* will not be very helpful, because it is likely that in such a biographical account, this particular form of the name will not appear at all: at the beginning of any particular biographical account, the full name will be used, which means that some other words will occur between *Abū Nuʿaym* and *al-Iṣbahānī*. Meanwhile, it is likely that in the rest of this biographical account, the writer will use only part of the name (e.g., *Abū Nuʿaym*). Thus, it is convenient to use (9) *Mufradāt mutabāʿida [wa]*, searching for the words *Nuʿaym* and *al-Iṣbahānī* (you may have to try different spellings as well). This option is also helpful if you are looking for textual variants of a single *ḥadīth*.

(8) *Juzʾ min kalima/Part of a word* is very helpful for queries of a linguistic kind, such as examples of the usage of a word, or its derivatives.

Table-of-contents Search

Clicking *Mawāḍiʿ* opens the *Table-of-Contents Search* window (Pic. 7). On the right side of the window there is a chart with the names of chapters of all the books in the database (*al-Mawāḍiʿ*). The right column is *Names of Chapters (al-naṣṣ)*, the left column is *Book Titles (al-kitāb)*. Enter a word or a part of a word into the *Search Line*. Click *Baḥth/Search* to be brought instantly to the first search result (the page will automatically open in the *Page of the Book* window). The option *al-Natāʾij faqaṭ/Results Only* can be checked in order to view search results only. The *Navigation pane* can be used to browse the opened book.

Working with search results

After a search is initiated, the *Search Result Window* opens. It will take a few moments for the search to reach completion (Pic. 8). The *Search Results Table* is displayed in the lower half of the window: [1] Ordinal number of a search result; [2] Book title; [3] Volume; [4] Page; [5] Text (includes at least some searched-for words); [6] Search Result Status (*Tahdīd*). Search results can be browsed with the *Search Results Navigation Pane*. Also, a double-click on any search result opens a *Page of the Book* with the searched-for words. The *Navigation Pane* can be used to browse the opened book.

Search results can be reviewed in *Comparison Mode*, which is convenient for comparison with similar passages. To get to *Comparison Mode*, close the *Search Results* window and click

Muqāranāt to open Comparison Mode and select the *Natā'ij al-baḥth* bookmark to get to the search results.

Search results can be exported (see *Exporting Work Results*) and/or saved for further work. First, it is necessary to select the search results that you want to save. Any time you want to save the result of a search, you need to change its *Search Result Status (Taḥdīd)*, which is *False* by default. Click on *False* and then input “1” and push ‘Enter.’ This will change the status to *True*; input “0” to change the status back to *False*. Only items with the status of *True* can be saved. Other changes also can be made in the *Search Results Table* (such as typing in notes and comments, etc.). When you are done selecting items and making changes, click the *Save Button (Taḥzīn)*. This will open the *Naskh-Ḥifẓ-Tibā'a* window (see Pic. 9).

This window gives three options (the Arabic captions are confusing here):

- *Save Search Results (Ḥifẓ natījat al-baḥṭh)*. This option saves your search results into a database and allows you to review the results later. Enter a name for your search results (*ism al-milaff*) and click a button to save the selected search results into a database. Changes to the *Search Results Table* – if you have made any – will not be saved into a database. The results can be opened again from the *Search Window* (See Pic. 6): click (5) *Milaffāt al-baḥṭh*, then select a desired saved search to continue working with it.

- *Save a List of Search Results to a Text File (Naskh jadwal al-natā'ij ilā milaff)*. This option saves a list of search results to a text file. Only a list identical to a *Search Results* table from a *Search Results Window* will be saved. You can select a folder, where you can save the file. Enter a name for your search results (*ism al-milaff*) and click a button to save the selected search results. The text file with the results can be reviewed later; any changes to the *Search Results Table* will be saved.

- *Export a List of Search Results to a Text File (Ṭibāʿat jadwal natāʿij al-baḥth)*. This option is very similar to the previous one, except that it opens a text file (for printing), which can be saved afterward. You can select fields which you want to save: [1] Ordinal number of a search result; [2] Book title; [3] Volume; [4] Page; [5] Text.

Exporting Findings

Any findings in a database can be exported into a text file: this can be done during browsing in *Reading Mode* as well as during browsing the search results. The *Naskh/Copy* button, which is available in both modes, will open the *Saving/Exporting Texts* window (*Ḥifẓ al-nuṣūṣ*) (see Pic. 10).

In the *Exported Text* window you can select a desired portion of text to be exported or saved. If you have added any *Comments (Taʿlīq, see above)* to a page you are exporting, these will be visible, always beginning with the word *al-Taʿlīq*. Only comments in Arabic will be visible here.

Once it has been exported, every piece of text will be preceded by its *Text Coordinates*, which include an abbreviated title of the book, volume number, and page number.

If you need to save/export several pages, it is convenient to use *Notebooks* (*Mudhakkirāt*). *Quick Buttons* may be used for operations with *Notebooks*:

- (1) *Mash/Eraser*: erases all text from the *Exported Text* window.
- (2) *Hidhf/Delete*: deletes a selected notebook.
- (3) *Hifz ilā l-ḥāfiza/Copy to RAM*: copies selected text to memory (RAM), from which it can be pasted to any text editor.
- (4) *Hifz ilā milaff/Save to a file*: saves a selected portion of the text into a notebook. You will be asked to enter a name for your notebook; you can add any number of pages to the same notebook by entering the same name, when asked. When you are done

- adding pages to a notebook, click on a desired notebook to open it. On Pic. 10 you can see a notebook “ ١٠-٢ المنتظم ص ” opened.
- (5) *Ṭibā‘a/Export*: this button opens a text file with the selected text exported into it (you need to select text which you want to be exported). See Pic. 11 for example: on the top of the file there is a *List of Pages included in a file*. Then follows the text itself. Each page starts with the abbreviated name of the book, volume number and page number.
- (6) *Khurūj/Exit*: leaves the *Ḥifẓ al-nuṣūṣ* window.

Contents of Group 2 Databases²

Maktabat al-Adab al-‘Arabī. Version 1 (1 CD).

Published in 1419/1999, this library contains 32 books....

Maktabat al-Ta’rīkh wa-l-Ḥadāra al-Islāmiyya. Version 1.5 (1 CD).

As the title implies, this database contains books on different aspects of Islamic history, totaling 125 titles, most of which are multivolume. The great majority of the titles date from the classical period (very roughly, from the seventh to the fifteenth centuries CE/first to ninth centuries). Books within the database are divided into seven sections, which roughly correspond to different genres. The sections are as follows: [1] General History (*al-ta’rīkh al-‘āmm*); [2] Local histories (*tawārīkh al-buldān*); [3] Historical topics (*mawāḍi‘ tarīkhiyya*); [4] Biographical Literature (*al-ṭabaqāt wal-l-tarājim*); [5] Travels and Memoirs (*riḥlāt wa-mudhakkirāt*); [6] Miscellanea (*ukhrā*); [7] Reference works, Lexicons and Bibliographies (*ma‘ājim wa-[asmā’] al-kutub*). The principle governing the selection of books is not specified. The organization into sections sometimes appears somewhat confusing if not downright arbitrary (see the entire list of titles).

The first section, *General History*, contains 16 titles³. These are the best-known multivolume histories written in the Islamic world and in the Arabic language. Since they are

² For a full list of books included in these databases, see URL: ...

³ There are actually only 14 books: Ibn al-Jawzī’s *al-Muntaẓam* figures as two titles, a part covering events up until 257 AH, and a part covering events after that date. Al-Dhahabī’s *al-‘Ibar fī khabar man ghabar* is supplemented with an additional volume which contains information omitted in the main edition.

not that numerous, we may provide the entire list here, in chronological order. Please note that in what follows, dates are given according to the Hijra, or *Anno Hegirae* (AH); if two dates are given, the second is that of the Common Era (CE) or *Anno Domini* (AD).

The texts included in this section are the *Ta'rikh* of Khalīfa b. Khayyāṭ (d. 240); the *Ta'rikh* of al- Ya'qūbī (d. after 292/905); the *Ta'rikh al-umam wa-l-mulūk* (or *Ta'rikh al-rusul wa-l-mulūk*) of al-Ṭabarī (d. 310); the *Kitāb al-Bad' wa-l-ta'rikh* of al-Muṭahhar b. Ṭāhir al-Maqdisī (d. 507); the *Takmilat ta'rikh al-Ṭabarī* of Abū l-Faḍl al-Hamadhānī (d. 521); *Al-Muntazam* by Ibn al-Jawzī (d. 597/1201); *Al-Kāmil fī l-ta'rikh* by Ibn al-Athīr (d. 630); *al-Takmila li-Kitāb al-ṣila* by Ibn al-Abbār (d. 658); *al-'Ibar fī khabar man ghabar* by al-Dhahabī (d. 748); *al-Bidāya wa-l-nihāya* by Ibn Kathīr (d. 744); *Nafḥ al-ṭīb min ghuṣn al-Andalus al-raṭīb* by al-Maqqarī (d. 1041);⁴ *Shadharāt al-dhahab* by Ibn al-'Imād (d. 1089); *al-Ta'rikh al-Manṣūri* by Ibn Naẓīf (d. ???); and the *Ta'rikh 'ajā'ib al-āthār* by the modern Egyptian al-Jābartī (d. 825 or 826 CE).

The second section, *Local Histories*, contains 25 books. Chronologically speaking, these range from the *Faḍā'il Makka wa-l-sakan fihā* attributed to al-Ḥasan al-Baṣrī (d. 110/728) to the *Ta'rikh al-dawla al-'aliyya al-'uthmāniyya* by Muḥammad Farīd Bey (d. 1338/1919). Nonetheless, most of the books in this section are medieval, with 18 of them having been written before the eighth/fourteenth century, and eight of them dating from the seventh/thirteenth. They cover such regions as al-Maghrib and al-Andalus (six books), Egypt (four), Greater Syria (nine), the Arabian Peninsula (six), Iraq (four), Irān (two) and the Ottoman Empire (one). If we consider the local biographical dictionaries included in the *Ṭabaqāt wa-tarājim* section, the coverage becomes even more thorough. The most famous titles in this section include the two-volume *Futūḥ al-buldān* of al-Balādhurī (d. 279), the four-volume *Akḥbār Makka* of Muḥammad ibn Ishāq al-Fākihī (d. 275/885), the fourteen-volume *Ta'rikh Baghdād* of al-Khaṭīb al-Baghdādī (d. 463), and many others.

The third section, *Historical topics*, contains four books devoted to topics which the publishers of the databases did not assign to other sections. Here we find a monograph on the First *Fitna* (civil war) and the Battle of Camel, by Sayf b. 'Umar al-Asadī (d. 200/815), and a work on the murder of the caliph 'Uthmān, by Muḥammad b. Yaḥyā al-Mālaqī al-Andalusī (d. 741).

⁴ In Version 3.0 of this database, this book is placed in the *Local Histories* section.

The fourth section, *Biographical sources*, is the largest in terms of titles, containing 50 sources (72 titles in 3.0, of which 25 are new). This is the largest section in the database...

The fifth section, *Travels and Memoirs*, contains five books (six titles in 3.0; no new titles added), which include the travel accounts of Ibn Jubayr (d. 614/1217), Ibn Faḍlān (fl. in the early fourth/tenth century), and Ibn Baṭṭūṭa (d. 779/1377). The political memoirs of the 36th Ottoman Sulṭān ‘Abd al-Ḥamīd II (d. 1918 CE) are also included here.

The sixth section, *Miscellanea*, contains 12 books (15 titles in 3.0; five new titles), of which we should probably notice the following titles: *Masā’il al-Imām Aḥmad* [b. Ḥanbal] (d. 244); the *Aḥsan al-taqāsīm* of al-Muqaddasī (d. 390); Arabic translation of Persian works such as the *Safar-nāma* of Nāṣir-i Khusraw (d. between 465-471/1072-1078) and the *Siyāsāt-nāma* of Niẓām al-Mulk (d. 485/1092), the *Muqaddima* of Ibn Khaldūn (d. 808/1406), the *Ma’āthir al-ināfa fī ma’ālim al-khilāfa* of al-Qalqashandī (d. 821/1481), the *al-Shamārīkh fī ‘ilm al-tārīkh* by al-Suyūṭī (d. 911/1505) and others.

The seventh section, *Lexicons and Bibliographies*, contains 12 books. These are useful bibliographical and lexicographical references, mostly by medieval Arabic authors. Chronologically the titles of this section range from the *Fihrist* of Ibn al-Nadīm (d. 385) to a three-volume *Abdjadiyyat al-‘ulūm* by the Indian author al-Qannawjī (d. 1307/1890). This section also contains other classical reference works of bibliography, geography and lexicography, such as the two-volume *Kashf al-ẓunūn* of Ḥājjī Khalīfa (d. 1067), the five-volume *Mu’jam al-buldān* of Yāqūt al-Ḥamawī (d. 626), the four-volume *al-Fā’iq fī gharīb al-ḥadīth* of al-Zamakhsharī (d. 538), and the fifteen-volume *Lisān al-‘Arab* of Ibn Manẓūr (d. 711/1311). What is extremely helpful here is that all the Arabic dictionaries have been fully vocalized.

Maktabat al-‘Aqā’id wa-l-Milal. Ver 1.5 (1 CD).

Published in 1419/1999, this database contains 163 titles, divided into sections: [1] “General books” (*al-kutub al-jāmi‘a*) — 34 books; [2] “Doctrinal issues” (*mawāḍi‘ ‘aqdiyya*) — 29 books; [3] “Doctrines supported by Tradition” (*al-‘aqā’id al-musnada*) — 47 books; [4] “Religious groups and communities” (*al-firaq wa-l-milal*) — 9 books; [5] “Refutations” (*al-rudūd*) — 32 books; [5] “References works, Lexicons and Bibliographies” (*al-ma‘ājim wa-l-gharīb*) — 11 books.

Maktabat al-Ma‘ājim wa-l-Gharīb wa-l-Muṣṭalah. Version 1 (1 CD).

Published in 1419/1999, this contains 23 books, divided into three sections: [1] “Lexicons” (*al-ma‘ājim*); [2] “Technical terminology” (*al-Muṣṭalahāt*); [3] “Rare vocabulary” (*al-gharīb*).

This database has additional *quick buttons*: *al-Gharīb* opens dictionaries of rare words; *al-Muṣṭalah* opens dictionaries of technical terms; *al-Buldān* opens dictionaries of geographical terms; *al-Judhūr* opens lexicographic dictionaries. These are basically *Table-of-contents searches*, where the number of books is thematically limited.

Maktabat al-Turāth al-Siyāsī. Version 2 (1 CD).

Published in 1421/2000, this contains 39 books on different aspects of Islamic political theory and practice. The database does not have a section of lexicons and dictionaries.

Maktabat ‘Ulūm al-Ḥadīth. Version 1 (1 CD).

Published in 1421/2001, this database contains 47 books divided into two groups: [1] “The sciences of Ḥadīth” (*‘ulūm al-ḥadīth*) and [2] “Dictionaries of foreign and rare words” (*al-ma‘ājim wa-l-gharīb*).

Maktabat ‘Ulamā’ al-Islām. Version 1 (1 CD).

Published in 1421/2001, this database contains 62 books written by famous members of the Ḥanbalī school: seven books of Ibn Qudāma (d. 620), 11 books of Ibn al-Jawzī (d. 597/1201), 15 of Ibn Taymiyya (d. 728), 14 of Ibn Qayyim al-Jawziyya (d. 751), five of Ibn Rajab (d. 795), and eight books of al-Shawkānī (d. 1250). The database also has a small section of “Dictionaries of foreign and rare words” (*al-ma‘ājim wa-l-gharīb*), consisting of three books.

User’s Interface for Group 3 databases: Working with the Database

Main Window

When the program is started, it opens the initial window (Pic. T3-1 Main Window), where the user can see the *Main menu* and several buttons for the most frequently-used commands. The

interface for *Group 3* databases is similar to that of *Group 2*, with a few differences which may be considered improvements.

Main menu (from right to left)

8. *Milaff* / File

- a. *Muṭāta‘at kitāb* / Read a book: opens the list of books in the library (see Pic. T3-2 List of Books).
- b. *Khurūj* / Exit: click to close the program.

9. *Baḥth* / Search

- a. *‘Āmm* / General [search]: opens General Search window.
- b. *Mawḍū‘ī* / Table-of-contents search: opens Table-of-contents search.
- c. *Tarājim* / Biographical search: opens *al-Rijāl* search window.

10. *Adawāt* / Tools

- a. *Al-Gharīb wa-l-ma‘ānī* / Dictionaries & Lexicons: opens Linguistic search window.

11. *Khidmāt* / Services

- a. *Ta‘līqāt* / Comments: opens a list of comments to a currently open book.
- b. *Khuṭūṭ* / Font Properties: changes font face and size.
- c. *Alwān* / Font color: changes font color.
- d. *Naskh* / Copy: opens Copy window.

12. *Iṣḍārātunā* / Our products: open to read annotations to other programs developed and published by al-Turāth.

13. *Ḥawla* / About

- a. *Al-Barnamaj* / About the Program: opens a window with details about the version of the program.
- b. *Musā‘ada* / Help: opens a Table of contents window for the Help function.

[Pic. T3-1 Main Window]

Quick buttons are most often used commands, which are collected on a separate toolbar for prompt access (from right to left):

- *Kitāb* opens the List of available books (see Pic. T3-2).
- *Kitābayn* opens Comparison mode (similar to that of Group 2; please, refer to the relevant section above).
- *Hāshiya* opens a window, in which comments to a currently open page can be added (similar to *Ta'liq* function in Group 2).
- *Biṭāqa* opens a card with all available details about the paper edition, on which the currently open digital book is based (same as in Group 2; for a detailed description, please refer to the relevant section above).

- *Khuṭūṭ* changes font face and size.
- *Alwān* changes font color.
- *Lawn al-khalfiyya* changes the background color.
- *Naskh* opens the Saving/Exporting Texts window (same as in *Group 2*; for a detailed description, please refer to the relevant section above).
- *Baḥṭh* opens the General Search window.
- *Mawḍūʿ* opens the Table-of-contents search.
- *Tarājim* opens the *al-Rijāl* search window.
- *Milaffāt* opens the Saved Search Results window.
- *Natāʾij* opens the Previous Search results.
- *Maʿnā* opens the Dictionaries search window.
- *Akhṭāʾ* opens a list of corrections made by the user; you can use this function to add any corrections of typos discovered on the currently open page.
- *Īdāh* opens help for the currently open window, providing detailed explanation for all functions.
- *Ḥawla* opens a window with details about the version of the program.

Reading Mode

When a user begins working with a database, he/she will usually either open a book to read or will initiate a search from among any number of available types. Clicking *Kitāb* (or *Muṭālaʿat kitāb*) will bring the user to the List of Books (*Qāʾimat asmāʾ al-kutub*) window (see picture below).

The List of Books is divided into sections, the names of which are in bold black and underlined. Since the number of books in Group 3 databases is usually much larger than in Group 2 databases, it is convenient to use *Quick Search* (type any word and click the *Binocular* button to move to the first found item; click it again to move to the next found item). Click the *Open* button to start reading a selected book.

The functionality of the Reading mode (see Pic. T3-3 Reading Mode) is very similar to that of Group 2 databases. The user can browse the open book by using the *Book Navigation Pane* and/or the Table of Contents, which is searchable with the TOC Search Pane. Comparison Mode is accessible with the *Kitābayn* button (similar to that of Group 2, please refer to the relevant section above); use the *Kitāb* button to select another book. Recently-viewed books can be accessed via the *Recently-Viewed Books* list. For more details, please refer to the relevant section above.

[Pic. T3-2 List of Books]

[Pic. T3-3 Reading Mode]

Conducting Searches

The functionality of the search engine for Group 3 databases is the same as for Group *** . The only differences are the addition of a few pre-configured searches, and the search window's slightly different look. In addition to the two major kinds of searches – General Search and Tables-of-Contents Search – there are *Tarājīm* and *Ma'nā⁵* searches. General Search can also be used to retrieve similar information, but for specific purposes these searches more are convenient, since the range of sources they cover – biographical and linguistic dictionaries respectively – is pre-selected.

⁵ Also accessible via *Main menu* → *Adawāt* → *Al-Gharīb wa-l-ma'ānī*.

[Pic. T3-4 General Search]

The General Search window differs only in the way of selecting search range. The available options are as follows:

- all books: click *jami' al-kutub* to include all titles in the search range;
- sections: check the sections to be included in the range; click the [...] button next to the name of the section to select particular books in the section;
- particular books: click the *Fully Customizable Search Range* button (*Kiṭāq baḥth makḥṣūṣ*) to customize the search range; the button opens the entire list of books, where the user adds particular books into the search range and saves it into a file, which he/she can use later on. This option may be convenient when a user needs to work continuously with a certain set of sources.

Other types of searches are similar to what can be found in Group 2. The algorithms for working with search results and for saving/exporting findings are the same as well. For a detailed description, please refer to the relevant sections above.

Contents of *Group 3 Databases*⁶

al-Maktaba al-alfiyya li-l-sunna al-nabawiyya. Ver. 1.5 (1 CD).

(“The Library on the Prophetic Sunna, containing over a thousand books”). With around 1,300 volumes, this is one of the most helpful databases for researchers in *Ḥadīth*.

Maktabat al-fiqh wa-uṣūlih. Ver. 1.5 (1 CD)

(“The Library of Jurisprudence and Its Foundations”). This includes 900 volumes (mostly Sunnī Law).

⁶ For the full list of books, included in these databases, see URL: ...